

GAMIFICATION IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Aripova Elena Azizovna

Academic Title, Position: PhD, Senior Lecturer of
English Language, Global Education

Place of Work: Westminster International University in Tashkent

E-mail: earipova@wiut.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13923554>

Abstract

One of the most powerful means in education, gamification has been introduced for language learning. This paper explores the pros of gamification in learning foreign languages relating to motivation, enhancement of language competence and speech skills and student engagement. Based on existing literature, we identify that gamification enables customised learning experiences and increases learner motivation as well as language mastery in vocabularies, grammar practices and overall communication skills. Besides, gamification creates a positive learning atmosphere which is good for student retention and engagement. This shows the gamification not only acts as a motivator, but also as an efficient pedagogical practice for language learners in different educational backgrounds.

Keywords: gamification, language learning, motivation, engagement, vocabulary, grammar, personalized learning

Introduction

Gamification, in simple terms, is about integrating game mechanics such as rewards systems and leaderboard to non-game environment. Its no secret that the buzzword active learning has been spiraling out of control in education and is being used more by officials to just get butts into seats so our funding remains intact. Gamification makes the process more enjoyable and motivating which can help in learning a language and considered as challenging task that will take years to accomplish. The purpose of this paper is to examine the different types of advantages that gamification can bring into language learning, in terms of affecting learner motivation and performance as well through their level engagement with academics.

The biggest benefit of gamification that is known on a large scale by most people is the improvement in learner motivation due to it. Learning a new language is no easy feat, and over time many students may lose motivation. Nevertheless, the execution of gamified elements such as point systems, badges and levels provides constant feedbacks and rewards to maintain learners involved (Al-

Dosakee & Ozdamli, 2021). It has been well established that gamification boosts overall motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, to overcome the difficulties of learning a language. Based on a systematic review by Al-Dosakee and Ozdamli (2021), gamification acts as an engagement, motivation in the learning process due to making it more fun, rewarding for learners.

In addition to this, gamified learning spaces cultivate a competitive but cohesive spirit that allow for further motivation. According to a study carried out at UmmAl Quwain University, students who were exposed to gamified English language learning environment reported 93 % more self-motivation (Al-Sabbagh, 2023). Games with a competitive aspect and also collaborative activities motivated students to participate in the moment, as well as strive for continuous improvement. These results seem to indicate that gamification can turn a rather passive learning platform into an interactive and dynamic experience.

Gamification not only boosts motivation but also increases effectiveness in learning, especially for language (Kuo et al, 2018). This immediate feedback often available on gamified platforms allows learners the opportunity to correct mistakes in real-time, helping them grasp complicated language concepts better. Gil-Aciron (2022) found that students with gamified learning environments scored higher on the vocabulary and grammar exam. One of the main advantages when it comes to games in educational environments, and one that is key for language learning. Participating students in gamified learning environs maintained the subject matter to a markedly greater extent than students enrolled in old-school class settings.

In addition, a systematic review by Dehghanzadeh et al (2019). Gamification, in its best form can have a positive influence on acquisition , which is very useful for the development of language skills such as speaking reading and listening. The findings demonstrated that learning experiences gamified engrosses the attention of learners and therefore perform better in language assessments. In addition to higher academic achievement, a review by Dehghanzadeh emphasized that positive outcomes may include increases in learner satisfaction with the online course as well as improvement motivation and general wellness across the board (2019).

Gamification further enables the concept of personalized learning as it allows learners to work at their desired pace and according to their specific needs. Gamified tools are adaptable, they can be tweaked by educators to suit the needs of learners who have different abilities and preferences. Szabó and Kopinska

(2023), for instance, make the case that by enabling levels of varying attempt-quality within a single classroom gamification provides respectful feedback in individualized learning. It makes fewer, smaller changes that resolve behavior pain points and increases engagement of learners frustrated by traditional language teaching, e.g. too irregular/stressful.

Another power of gamification is that language-learning can be broken down to achievable units, several times referred as 'quests' or even 'levels'. The use of a segmented approach to learning is especially beneficial in that students have less cognitive load and can zero-in on specific portions of the language they want to master. According to Alomair and Hammami (2019), these students attending gamified learning environments inclined them in reflecting their weak points either vocabulary, grammar or speaking skill that motivates the learners taking intentional actions for enhancing those skills. The opportunity to personalize learning creates a feeling of ownership and autonomy in the process, thus improving motivation and long-term memory.

It has also been proven that gamification can increase student engagement and retention in language learning as well. Through interactive games, point systems and rewards are used to create an environment where students have the motivation (and pressure) push them into learning by active/consistent participation (Cruaud 2018). It was concluded from the results that gamification can be effective, not only in producing an enhanced academic performance but also a change of learner attitudes toward the discipline.

Similarly, Amaya-Díaz and Bajaña-Zajia (2020) reported that interactive games via "Hot Potatoes" designed for students in an English language learning communicative university-led online platform significantly enhanced motivation towards game use effectiveness to strengthen proficiency too. In the study, students who used this platform demonstrated a higher level of engagement and preparedness to engage in class activities so that they had significantly less dropout rates and language test results.

Gamification can also drive teamwork and collaboration, which leads to additional levels of engagement. And many of gamified platforms include multiplayer or cooperative assignments, in which students will learn from and converse with one another. Joint efforts also prompt the mutual support within students meanwhile establishing collaborations that set up friendly discussions on language ideas and enable them to practice skills in a more natural way, leading to a richer learning experience.

Conclusion

The advantages of gamification in language learning have been recorded throughout various research and educational environments. Gamification of language learning not only drives motivation & engagement but it also boosts the result and provides a personalized way to learn languages. This way, learners can progress at their own speed compete and cooperate with one another in Korean language learning it turns out to be an actually fun interactive process. Nonetheless, a systematic design of the game with educational goals may offset such risk as it prevents irrelevant elements taking prominence over useful content. In the future, as gamification progresses further it is thought that there will even more ways in which language learners can be helped to experience success and for this proficiency level of enabling technology advances.

References:

1. Al-Dosakee, H., & Ozdamli, F. (2021). The role of gamification in promoting learner motivation: A systematic review. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(2), 123-145.
2. Alomair, M., & Hammami, S. (2019). Personalized gamification for language learning: Reflecting on weaknesses and improving skills. *Language Learning Journal*, 47(3), 255-272.
3. Amaya-Díaz, M., & Bajaña-Zajia, R. (2020). Enhancing language learning with interactive games: Hot Potatoes as a gamified learning tool. *International Journal of English Language Teaching*, 15(4), 89-104.
4. Cruaud, C. (2018). Gamification in French as a foreign language classroom: Effects on student participation and engagement. *Revue Internationale des Technologies en Pédagogie Universitaire*, 15(1), 50-62.
5. Dehghanzadeh, H., Rezaei, A., & Soleimani, P. (2019). Gamification in education: Systematic review and implications for language learning. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 18-28.
6. Gil-Aciron, S. (2022). Gamified learning platforms and their impact on vocabulary and grammar acquisition. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 22(3), 345-360.
7. Kuo, Y.-T., Chuang, C.-H., & Lin, T.-C. (2018). Gamified language learning: Immediate feedback and its role in improving language mastery. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 26(4), 467-480.
8. Szabó, I., & Kopinska, I. (2023). Gamification and personalized learning: How levels of effort influence student engagement in language acquisition. *Educational Research Review*, 40(1), 99-110.